

The Top 100 Most Cited Articles on Machine Learning in the Subject Area of Physics

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Abstract

Today, mankind has an easier life due to the advancement of science. Machine learning is an example of the advancement of science in industries and appliances. Machine learning is a sub-branch of artificial intelligence. In this bibliometric study, the best articles in the field of machine learning and physics subject area were analyzed. A bibliometric study helps to identify the most emerging research topics, and highest influential authors, journals and countries. There were 11,603 documents on SCOPUS database on the selected research area. The top 100 ones were selected for further quantitative analysis by VOSviewer software. The top ten documents were short reviewed and analyzed qualitatively. There was a significant growth in the publication in recent years. The most emerging keywords in the research area were “COVID-19”, “artificial intelligence”, and “materials informatics”. The findings of this research may help future researchers to select their favorite documents from the top journals which introduced in this study based on the emerging keywords in the research area of machine learning in the subject area of physics.

Keywords: Machine Learning, Physics, Bibliometrics, Artificial Intelligence, Highly Cited, Publication Trends, Top Papers, Top Cited

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Introduction

Machine Learning (ML) is the study of algorithms that learn from data [1]. Among other definitions, ML is defined as the scientific field that gives machines the ability to learn without being strictly programmed. ML applies in more and more scientific fields including, bioinformatics, biochemistry, medicine, meteorology, economic sciences, robotics, aquaculture, food security, climatology, and physics. The most recent publications which received the highest citations were working on cosmology intertwined [2], nanophotonic biosensors [3], circular business models [4], quantum algorithms [5], fault diagnosis of power transformers [6], thermal conductivity [7], social physics [8], personalized healthcare [9], applications of wireless sensor networks and internet of things [10], and simulation tool for particle-based materials [11]. Researchers need tools to evaluate scholarly output in ML research. Bibliometric analysis is a powerful tool for quantitatively investigating scientific outputs [12]. A bibliometric study analysis indicators such as the number of published articles, citations, and collaborating networks for measuring research output performance [13]. Two of the most important indicators for a bibliometric analysis are the number of published articles and citations.

There were six bibliometric analyses applied in different fields of study including “Application analysis of machine learning in fault diagnosis” [14], “Machine-learning-based digital twin in manufacturing” [15], “Citation likelihood analysis of the interbank financial networks literature: A machine learning and bibliometric approach” [16], “Recent synergies of machine learning and neurorobotics” [17], “Machine learning and automl in crash severity prediction” [18], and “Machine learning and big data in the impact literature” [19]. However, from one side, none of these studies directly concentrates on Machine Learning in the subject area of physics. On the other side, the previously published studies have not treated the bibliometric approach in the field of the top 100 most cited articles to the best of our current knowledge. Therefore, the objectives of this study are to answer the following research questions. The study seeks to answer the following three research questions (RQs):

- RQ1. What are the publication trends?
- RQ2. What are the most influential journals?
- RQ3. What are research hotspots?

Methodology

The SCOPUS was selected for data collection due to the broad coverage in comparison with Web of Science (WoS) [20]. The data were collected on October 16, 2022. A title search of “machine learning” in the subject area of physics, was run on SCOPUS databases SCOPUS and retrieved 11,603 documents. Figure 1 illustrated the research flow diagram adapted from PRISMA [21]. The top 100 documents were selected based on the number of citations per year (TCpY). It means the top 100 documents received the highest citation rate among all 11,603 documents. The “visualization of similarities”, VOSviewer software [22] was used for quantitative bibliometric analysis. The VOSviewer software is able to find the most emerging keywords in a specific area of research. At the final stage, the top ten documents were selected for qualitative analysis.

Figure 1 The research flow diagram

Results and Discussions

Table 1 shows the distributions of 11,603 document types of machine learning in the physics subject area. The majority (n = 11,039; 95.14%) were articles and conference papers. Other document type consists of 24 conference review, 16 letters, eight books, five short surveys, and two undefined.

Table 1 Document types of machine learning in the physics subject area

Document Type	NO.	Percentage
Article	6,369	54.89%
Conference Paper	4,670	40.25%
Review	274	2.36%
Book Chapter	66	0.57%
Erratum	54	0.47%
Editorial	45	0.39%
Note	35	0.30%
Retracted	35	0.30%
Other	55	0.47%

7th International Conference on Applied Research in Basic Sciences, Engineering and Technology

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Publication Trends

The annual publication trends and the cumulative number of publications are shown in Figure 2. From 1984 to 2008, the annual number of publications on Machine learning did not see any change; remaining at less than 15 documents per year. From 2008 to 2020, there was an obvious increase in the annual number of publications. The data were collected on October 16, 2022. Therefore, the year 2022 data were not completed and the declining trend should not be considered.

Figure 2. Number of publications per year and the cumulative number of publications in the research area from 1984 – 2023

Keywords Analysis

Keywords co-occurrence analysis is employed to identify and explore leading and emerging topics in the "Machine Learning" research area. Analyzing the co-occurrence frequencies of the keywords in publication can provide insights into main topics and research trends. VoSviewer software is used to visualize the outcomes of co-occurrence frequencies of the keywords. the author's top 11 keywords out of 167 keywords used in the previous citation are shown in Figure 3. The size of each node indicates the frequencies occurrence of the keywords and the links between the nodes represent the co-occurrence between the keywords. The most emerging keywords were "COVID-19" followed by "artificial intelligence", and "materials informatics".

7th International Conference on Applied Research in Basic Sciences, Engineering and Technology

March 14, 2023

Tbilisi - Georgia

Figure 3. Top author's keywords

Top Journals

The cluster view of the most influential journals in the field of "machine learning" is shown in Figure 4. Based on a clustering technique, the journals in the data set were divided into three clusters illustrated in Red, Green, and Blue colours. The map shown in Figure 4 was constructed based on the journal co-citation data set. According to Figure 2, the most influential journals with the highest total link strength of 42 and 38 were "Physical Review Letters" and "Physical review B" respectively. However, journals with the highest numbers of citations received were "Physical review letters" and "nature communications" with 3,455 and 1,650 citations respectively. These sources plus "Physical review B – Condensed matter and materials physics" belong to the Green cluster. The most influential sources make easier the reviewing process by selecting papers from those particular journals. The Red cluster consists of "computer physics communications", "international journal of quantum chemistry", "journal of chemical physics" and "physical review x". The "computational materials science" journal belongs to the Blue cluster with five total link strengths and 349 citations.

7th International Conference on Applied Research in Basic Sciences, Engineering and Technology

March 14, 2023

Tbilisi - Georgia

Figure 4. Cluster diagram of the most influential journals

Qualitative Analysis

The top ten documents which received the highest citations per year were selected for qualitative analysis. The top ten documents abstract were read by at least two of co-authors separately and make down the important themes. The final results were extracted after some careful discussions on the selected themes. Table 2 illustrates research hotspots highlighted in the top ten documents. The documents should receive at least one hundred citations per year for inclusion in Table 2. The review papers usually receive more citations [23]. As indicated in the table 60% of top ten documents types were review papers. The majority of high-ranked publications prove the finding of “Author’s Keywords analysis”. Since all the articles were in the field of machine learning, another column with this name was not added in the table. Future research may investigate why these documents received the highest number of citation per year by a comprehensive review approaches.

Table 2 Research hotspots highlighted in the top ten documents

NO.	References	TC	TCpY	Fluid mechanics	Differential Equations	Neural Networks	Artificial intelligence	Health care	Covid-19	Predicting	Atomic positions	Modeling	Statistic	Document Type
1	Brunton, et al. [24]	677	225.67	X								X		R
2	Karniadakis, et al. [25]	353	176.50		X	X								R
3	Carleo, et al. [26]	673	168.25									X	X	R
4	Liakos, et al. [27]	816	163.20				X			X				R
5	Loey, et al. [28]	297	148.50						X					A
6	Samaniego, et al. [29]	410	136.67		X	X								A
7	Carrasquilla and Melko [30]	760	126.67			X								A
8	Linardatos, et al. [12]	252	126.00				X	X						R
9	Lalmuanawma, et al. [31]	333	111.00				X	X	X	X				R
10	Rupp, et al. [32]	1151	104.64							X	X		X	A

(TC=Time Cited, and TCpY=Time Cited per Year, R=Review, A=Article)

Conclusions

This article presents a short qualitative and quantitative analysis based on published scientific literature in “Machine Learning in the subject area of physics” research retrieved from SCOPUS databases from 1984 to October 16, 2022. Analysis of publications showed an increasing trend with respect to time, especially after 2008, indicating the machine learning (ML) growth in this specific area. This rapid increase in the number of publications is an indicator of the potential growth of ML in the subject area of physics in upcoming years. Analysis of keyword shows the emerging keywords of “COVID-19”, “artificial intelligence”, and “materials informatics”. Analysis of sources indicated that the highest number of citations received were "Physical review letters" and "nature communications". Whereas, the most influential journals with the highest link strength were "Physical Review Letters" and "Physical review B". The qualitative analysis of the top ten highly cited publications has also confirmed this budge. This paper is the first bibliometric study on the top 100 most cited articles on ML in the subject area of physics to explain ML research's current advances and future directions. This paper is helpful to the researchers to identify the most important publications, journals and to identify the associated research areas of their specific research interests. Moreover, by suggesting the emerging keywords, it gives a valuable insight to the emerging research direction.

List of Symbols

Abbreviation	Definition
A	Article
ML	Machine Learning
R	Review
RQs	Research Questions
TC	Time Cited
TCpY	Time Cited per Year
WoS	Web of Science

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